

Comparative study of social studies curriculum in scandinavian countries in developing students' social skills

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ABSTRACT

Social skills play a central role in shaping individuals who are able to adapt and contribute to society. This article analyzes the comparative social studies curriculum in Scandinavian countries (Denmark, Norway and Sweden), focusing on how students' social skills are developed through their approach to learning. The research method used is a qualitative approach with an emphasis on document analysis and uses a horizontal descriptive approach in the context of comparative education. The results of the comparison found that Denmark emphasizes the integration of social skills in practical learning and research projects, Norway through an integrated approach with its contemporary issues while Sweden applies innovation through technology and community involvement. The comparison between the three countries revealed similarities, differences, as well as challenges and successes in the development of students' social skills. The conclusions of this analysis provide a foundation for recommending best practices and improvements in social studies curriculum, which can be applied globally to enhance students' social skills development in this modern era.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In an era of constant change and rapidly evolving globalization, it is important for the education system to not only provide academic knowledge, but also develop critical social skills for students. Social skills, such as the ability to communicate, cooperate and solve problems, are an important foundation for preparing future generations. This article aims to analyze the comparative social studies curriculum in the Scandinavian countries of Denmark, Sweden and Norway, focusing on how students' social skills are developed through their approach to social studies learning. In Table 1 we can see the basic principles associated with the following social skills indicators [1].

Social studies is an important subject that equips students with the skills to participate, engage and deliberate as members of society. The subject will help students to recognize the relationship between individual choices, the structure of society and the limits of tolerance in nature. In social science, students will have the opportunity to explore their own identity, the local community in which they live and national and global challenges [2]–[5]. Reviewing the information from attachment: Table 1 shows that the social studies curriculum plays a key role in shaping students' worldview and providing a deep understanding of

society and its dynamics. Social studies education has an important role in forming socially and culturally intelligent students, including in understanding and practicing conflict resolution [6]. This is inseparable from the purpose of social studies learning, which is to create the next generation of a good, noble and nationalistic nation. This seems to have been addressed in the social science education curriculum at the primary and secondary levels in Sweden [7], i.e. showing awareness of the importance of understanding social, political and civic issues in society.

Table 1. Dimensions of social skills indicators

No	Content	Description
1	Planning with others	For example, how to divide up the tasks involved in preparing the group's written report, or how to decide who will look for answers to some of the study questions
2	Participate in research projects	Such as a committee effort to research an issue of common concern, or working in two or more small groups to investigate a specific topic.
3	Participate productively in group discussions	Through developing confidence in the ability to contribute ideas and information to others
4	Respond politely to others' questions	Through learning to listen to what others are asking and then responding appropriately
5	Lead group discussion	Through learning how to ask the right questions, how to encourage others to speak, and how to refocus and clarify other responses
6	Act responsibly	Through predicting the consequences of certain actions and taking responsibility for initiated actions
7	Helping others	Through providing assistance when someone has information that will make it easier for others to succeed in a given task

The same is true in the country of Ukraine [8] education standards outline the basic competencies that students are expected to possess, namely the ability to act as responsible citizens, participate in social and political life, and understand social, economic, and political concepts, and include developing the ability to cooperate, respect others, resolve conflicts, and understand human rights, cultural diversity, and personal identity as citizens of Ukraine. Likewise, in other developed countries [9]–[14], in these countries gives us an insight that social science education plays an important role in shaping young citizens who are ready to participate in social life, have a deep understanding of civic values, and are able to contribute to the positive development of society and the state. Thus, this paper is important to be developed further and is also supported by the study that only a few studies have been conducted on literacy skills in social studies education [15]–[17]. Students will learn how geographical, historical, and current events are the foundation for societies to meet their needs, and how power and resources are distributed. Students will learn that we are not only shaped by history, but we also shape history. The subject should contribute to developing students' understanding of their individual identities, and of the diversity of the communities we belong to. This means that the subject is studied through both majority and minority perspectives with a particular focus on Sami cultures and communities. As such, social studies will help strengthen students' understanding of themselves, of the society in which they live and the ways in which they can influence their own lives and the future.

All subjects should help students to understand the value system in learning. Social studies should help students to become engaged, critical, innovative and explorative thinkers, and should support attitudes and values such as tolerance, equality, and respect. By using social studies approaches and methodologies, students will develop into active citizens based on knowledge of democracy, the environment, human rights, equality, and the value of diversity. Thus, it is important to understand that knowledge alone is not enough; students need to be equipped with strong social skills in order to successfully adapt to the complex changes in today's global society.

In this context, Scandinavian countries were chosen to be the focus of the research, each representing a unique approach to integrating social skills into their social studies curriculum. Scandinavia is known as a centre of educational innovation. Innovative initiatives, progressive learning methods and an emphasis on developing students' skills have gained international attention [18], [19]. In addition, universities in Scandinavian countries are also highly ranked internationally. For example, universities in Sweden and Denmark [20] can be found in the world's leading university rankings. This is also supported by the curriculum in Scandinavia [7], [21], [22] which often includes actual and relevant social issues especially in the field of social science education. By exploring the differences and similarities between the approaches of these Scandinavian countries, we can gain a better insight into how students' social skills are applied and developed in three different educational contexts. With this understanding, we can explore how best to improve social studies curricula in different countries and ensure that education provides comprehensive provision for future generations, especially in Indonesia.

2. METHOD

This research takes a qualitative approach with an emphasis on document analysis and uses a horizontal descriptive approach in the context of comparative education. The document analysis method, as described by Yildirim and Simsek [23], this research was implemented to investigate information in written materials related to the phenomenon or event that is the focus of the research. This research explores the Danish education curriculum in social studies (Grades 8-9) [22]. Norwegian education curriculum in social studies (grades 8-10) [21] and Swedish education curriculum in social studies (grades 7-9) [7]. The interpretation process is carried out by comparing the results of the curriculum review with the principles of social skills, which include aspects of the ability to plan with others, participate in research projects, participate productively in group discussions, respond politely to other people's questions, lead group discussions, act responsibly, and help others [1]. This research is limited to the focus of the social studies curriculum in Denmark in 2019, Norway in 2020 and Sweden in 2011. This approach is expected to provide in-depth insight into the comparison of the social studies curriculum in Scandinavian countries in the context of social skills development.

The scope of this research lies in examining the social studies curriculum in Denmark, Norway, and Sweden. These curricula were selected because it was considered that the learning materials in these areas were more closely related to the development of social skills. The analysis of these curricula focused on understanding the extent to which learning concepts and content can support the development of social skills, including aspects of the ability to plan with others, participate in research projects, participate productively in group discussions, respond politely to others' questions, lead group discussions, act responsibly, and help others. The selection of these curricula was considered a strategic step to explore the implementation of social skills in learning structures, teaching methods and curriculum materials in the context of social studies learning in Denmark, Norway, and Sweden. This analysis is expected to provide in-depth insights into the role of curriculum in facilitating students' social skills development in these three countries.

This research focuses on analyzing the principles of social skills, which include the dimensions of social interaction, communication skills, and sensitivity to social issues. The research data involved social studies curricula in three countries (Denmark, Norway, and Sweden). The data were analyzed with reference to the established social skills principles as shown in Table 1. In the context of learning outcomes and learning areas, the curricula studied were compared with the social skills principles.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To comprehend the impact of the social studies curriculum on the development of students' social skills, this discourse will delve into several pivotal findings from three noteworthy countries: Denmark, Norway, and Sweden. By exploring and comparing the diverse approaches and strategies employed in the cultivation of social skills across these nations, a profound insight into the global diversity within education systems emerges. Denmark, Norway, and Sweden serve as compelling case studies, each offering unique perspectives on how social studies curricula contribute to shaping students' abilities to navigate societal interactions. Through this comparative lens, we can unearth nuanced insights into the cultural, pedagogical, and societal factors that influence the methodologies adopted in these countries. The examination of these distinctive approaches not only enriches our understanding of the specific intricacies within each national education system but also contributes to a broader comprehension of the global landscape in social studies education. Furthermore, this comparative analysis goes beyond a mere enumeration of differences; it seeks to identify commonalities and shared challenges. By doing so, we aim to extract universal principles that can potentially inform and enhance social studies curricula on a global scale. The intention is not just to highlight disparities but to foster a holistic understanding of the multifaceted nature of social studies education, acknowledging that effective strategies may vary but overarching principles can be identified and adapted universally. In essence, this exploration aims to contribute to the ongoing discourse on the role of social studies in shaping well-rounded individuals capable of thriving in diverse and interconnected societies.

3.1. Analysis of the Danish state social studies curriculum in social skills development

Studying social studies is an important subject in the Danish education system. It is seen as a necessary subject to make students ready for citizenship, and it is also a subject that enhances students' abilities for further and higher education. The focus on working at different taxonomic levels in social science is a very important way to improve academic skills and make students aware of how to analyze social issues. Denmark uses the term *Samfundsfag* to refer to the subject of social studies. Since its introduction in the 1960s, social studies in Denmark have been a blend of elements from the basic social sciences: economics, sociology, politics, and international politics as well as methods in the social sciences. This broad and extensive approach of integrating aspects from different social sciences into the teaching of social studies has some great advantages but also provides some challenges for teaching [22]. In summary, the Danish

social studies curriculum can be seen in Table 2 where the table describes the position of social studies at each level, although this paper focuses on social studies at the junior high school level, but in general it will also describe social studies at the primary school level, senior high school and vocational high school.

Table 2. Overview of social studies curricula in Denmark

Education unit	Grade level	Content	Methods	Evaluation
Folkeskole	8-9	Sociology; Politics; Economics	Combining social science theories with issues and problems in society (integrated)	Oral exam
Almen gymnasium	C-D	Denmark and globalization issues.	Discussion	Oral exam
Almen gymnasium	A	International politics and globalization.	Out-of-class activities	Written exam
Erhvervs gymnasium	C-A	Social studies is studied at level C and is an option at level B, while Level A can choose international economics/business economics	Small research project Debate activity	Oral exam

In this discussion, we will refocus on social studies at the junior secondary school level. As mentioned, social studies consist of core elements of sociology, economics, politics, and international politics. Further elaboration of the detailed content of this material includes sociology, for example identity, social differentiation in Denmark and other countries and the media. Politics, e.g. political ideologies, concepts of power and democracy and political decision-making. Economics, e.g. welfare principles, market economy, globalization, and macroeconomic policy. And international politics, e.g. power, security, conflict and international integration. The curriculum appears to engage students in the analysis, presentation, and discussion of social issues.

The importance of oral exam-based assessment in the learning context. This assessment relies entirely on the results of oral exams, which are organized by teachers in collaboration with seniors from other schools. The setting of the oral exam is designed for students to develop a number of competencies, including in-depth understanding of a topic, presentation writing skills, and oral dialogue abilities. Thus, students are expected to not only master the subject but also be able to analyze, present, and discuss social issues. The entire structure of the oral exam is based on students' ability to master different levels of the taxonomy. As such, the oral exam aims to provide students with a solid preparation for social studies at the senior high school level. Based on the description of the social studies curriculum in Denmark, we will try to draw a relationship or linkage of this social studies curriculum to the attention of the Danish government in developing social skills to its students, by referring to the learning objectives along with the expected competencies and learning methods used by teachers in this country to teach social studies subjects at grade 8-9, we can see based on the following Table 3.

Table 3. Relationship between social studies curriculum and social skills principles

Level	Outcome learning	Competence	Methods	Principles of social skills
8-9	Students gain knowledge about society and historical change	Analyze and discuss social problems	Integrated, discussion, out-of-class activities, small research projects, debates	(1), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
	Students are able to take an active part in a democratic society	Analyze and discuss social problems	Integrated, discussion, out-of-class activities, small research projects, debates	(1), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
	Students are able to contribute to students' understanding of themselves and others as part of a society that they can influence and be influenced by	Analyze and discuss social problems	Integrated, discussion, out-of-class activities, small research projects, debates	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
	Students are able to understand daily life in a social and historical perspective	Analyze and discuss social problems	Integrated, discussion, out-of-class activities, small research projects, debates	(1), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
	Students have knowledge and skills in politics (power, decision-making and democracy), economics (production, employment and consumption) and social and cultural conditions (socialization, culture and identity).	Analyze and discuss social problems	Integrated, discussion, out-of-class activities, small research projects, debates	(1), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)

Source: Curriculum content adapted from Danish social studies curriculum [22].

The Danish definition of social studies emphasizes the integration of social science theories with community issues and problems. Flexibility of teaching is emphasized, where the selection of theories can be

adjusted, without a fixed curriculum. The main aim of the teaching is to provide students with analytical tools to examine the development of society, enabling them to develop personal viewpoints on a more solid basis. Thus, the Danish approach to social studies leads to providing an in-depth knowledge base and fostering students' analytical skills in understanding the dynamics of society.

Second, it aims to promote democratic and quality discussion, not only providing students with knowledge and analytical tools, but also preparing them to actively participate in democracy [24]. Focus involves preparing students to be responsible citizens. Social studies are not just an academic subject, but a crucial element that encourages active engagement and responsibility of students. Third, social studies is therefore integral in shaping a sense of citizenship among students [25], [26]. Social studies are not just an academic subject, but a crucial element that encourages students' active engagement and responsibility. Social studies are therefore integral in shaping a sense of citizenship among students.

3.2. Analysis of Norwegian social studies curriculum in social skills development

Like Denmark, Norway also uses the term Samfunnsfag to refer to social studies. Is based on the Kunnskapsdepartementet report, which states that social studies classroom practice in Norway is often supported by textbooks and talks, with a lack of activities involving complex projects and cooperation. Although professional practice with the selection and curation of learning resources by teachers can be found in some schools, it is uneven in all schools. A national strategy to improve the quality and cooperation of teacher education until 2025 has been prioritized [27]. In Norway, classroom practice predominantly involves the teacher speaking or holding class conversations, supported by textbooks. Teachers rarely talk for long periods of time, more often engaging students in dialog and peer-to-peer conversation.

Interactions between teachers and students in Norway tend to be more relaxed compared to the authoritarian, discipline-focused approach to teaching. The results of the teachers and school leaders as lifelong learners study show very good relationships between teachers and students in Norway, especially in social studies subjects. Teachers are perceived as authoritative, non-authoritarian, and supportive role models in both school and personal contexts. Although teachers in Norway teach relatively few hours (15.8 hours), they still prepare thoroughly for each class (6.3 hours), which results in a better ability to interact with students as a whole. However, novice teachers reported a lack of confidence in managing disruptive behavior in the classroom [18].

The use of digital learning tools in the country has become common since around 2010, with most classrooms digitized, equipped with broadband connections, and access to digital learning resources. Projectors or smart boards are common in many classrooms, facilitating the use of moving images. The availability of digital resources makes it easier to transition between classroom activities and is often used in the context of group work, projects and student presentations. The high variation (SD = 1.46) in the use of TV, film or photography reflects the diversity of approaches to integrating these media in Norwegian learning. In summary, the Norwegian social studies curriculum can be seen in Table 4 where the table outlined the position of social studies at each level, although this paper focuses on social studies at the junior high school level, but in general will also be described social studies at the elementary school level, and senior high school.

Table 4. Overview of social studies curricula in Norway

	Education Unit	Level	Content	Evaluation	
Group work Project	Barneskole	1-2	Political science, sociology, anthropology and social psychology, as well as law and criminology	In the form of analysis and comments from the teacher	Researcher/explorer
		3-4	Interdisciplinary topics; Health and life skills, Democracy and citizenship, and Sustainability	In the form of analysis and comments from the teacher	
		5-7	Researcher/explorer	In the form of analysis and comments from the teacher	
	Ungdomsskole	8-10	Level 10: Students can be pulled into an oral exam with a preparation section. The oral exam is prepared and censored locally		

Based on Table 4, it can be seen that the evaluation tools for primary schools do not have special tests. While teachers tend to include comments, analysis and sometimes non-official scores on the exams, the tests must be taken home and shown to parents. There are also introductory tests that give teachers information about how students are performing, whether they are above average or need help in school. The Norwegian education system covers primary school from levels 1 to 7, junior secondary school from levels 8 to 10, and senior secondary school from levels VG1 to VG3 [2]. Overall, these grading practices reflect efforts for transparency and parental involvement in monitoring and supporting students' academic

development at different levels of education. Based on the description of the social studies curriculum in Norway, then we will try to draw a relationship or linkage of this social studies curriculum to the attention of the Norwegian government in the development of social skills to students, by referring to the learning objectives along with the expected competencies and learning methods used by teachers in this country to teach social studies subjects at the level of grades 1-10, but because the focus of this paper is at the junior high school level, the meal to be analyzed is grades 8-10, this we can see based on the following Table 5.

Table 5. Relationship between social studies curriculum (levels 8-10) and social skills principles

No	Learning outcoming	Principles of social skills
1	Use social studies methods and digital resources in own research, and present findings using digital tools and discuss the validity and relevance of those findings	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
2	Assess how different sources provide information on social studies-related topics, and reflect on how algorithms, biased sources or lack of sources can affect our understanding.	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
3	Discuss how the way we view the past, events and groups have had and continue to have an impact on people's actions and attitudes·Explore how technology has been and continues to be a contributing factor to change, and discuss the effects of technology on individuals, society and nature.	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
4	Reflects on how people have struggled and continue to struggle for change in society, but is also influenced by geography and historical context	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
5	Compare how political, geographical and historical events affect living conditions, settlement patterns and demographics in different parts of the world today	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
6	Explain the causes and consequences of major past and contemporary conflicts, and reflect on whether changes in certain conditions could have prevented these conflicts.	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
7	Explain the causes and consequences of terrorism and genocide, such as the Holocaust, and reflect on how extremist attitudes and extremist actions can be prevented	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
8	Explore and explain how human rights and the rights of indigenous peoples, as well as international treaties and other international cooperation, are important for national policies, people's lives, equal rights and equality	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
9	Explain Norway's policies towards the Sami people and national minorities, as well as the injustices they have experienced, and thereby reflect on their impact and effects on an individual and societal level	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
10	Explain the different dimensions of sustainability and how they impact each other, and present steps that can be taken to make society more sustainable	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
11	Assess how employment, income and consumption can impact on one's personal finances, standard of living and quality of life· Reflect on equality and inequality in identities, ways of life and cultural expressions, and discuss opportunities and challenges related to diversity	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
12	Explore and reflect on one's digital footprint and the possibility of erasing one's digital footprint as well as the value of one's and others' rights to privacy, data protection and copyright	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
13	Reflects on how identity, self-image and boundaries are developed and challenged in different environments, and presents suggestions on how one can deal with unwanted influences and events	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
14	Reflect on which forces in society have power at the moment, and how they justify their position	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
15	Explore different platforms for digital interactions and reflect on how digital participation and digital interactions influence the shape and content of societal debates.	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
16	Explain important laws, regulations and norms and discuss the consequences of any possible violations on individuals and society, both in the short and long term	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
17	Describe the features of the current political system and welfare state in Norway and reflect on its main challenges.	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)

Source: Curriculum content adapted based on Norwegian social studies curriculum [21]

Referring to Tables 5 and 6, it can be seen that the Norwegian government's enthusiasm for education, especially in social studies subjects, is very planned and structured. We can see this from the indications of the goals that students want to achieve, the competencies that must be mastered and the learning methods that are considered unique. This condition certainly has an impact on the social skills possessed by students. results of the international civics and citizenship education study (ICCS) study in Norway in 2016, which provides an overview of the participation of 14-year-old students inside and outside school. This data, although valid for classes at school, is not limited to social studies subjects. Norwegian students in grade 9, at age 14, show a high level of knowledge about how democracy works, both in theory and practice, compared with the international average. Student participation in various activities, such as discussions, student council elections, school operations, as well as becoming student council candidates and improving the school environment, received the highest marks in Scandinavia and exceeded the international average. Women participate more actively and see teachers as more open to discussion compared to men. Despite high expectations for electoral participation, informal social and political participation in Scandinavia tends to be lower, but still above the international average. In terms of an open classroom

climate, Norwegian students rated their teachers as more open and supportive of discussion and conflict resolution, surpassing the international student average [28].

Table 6. Overview of the social sciences curriculum in Sweden (9 years of compulsory schooling)

Education units	Level	Content	Time allocation
Lagstadiet	1-3	Local democracy, such as school democracy, children's rights, family finances	200
Mellanstadiet	4-6	Sweden's democratic system and political parties, human rights, the role of taxes, mass media	70 (+33)
Hogstadiet	7-9	Ideology, democracy and dictatorship, function of democracy, international relations, public finance	75 (+35)

3.3. Analysis of the Swedish state social studies curriculum in social skills development

Social studies are a mandatory subject in every school year, with a curriculum that emphasizes the development of disciplinary knowledge and citizenship education. Although Sweden has a growing research community in this field, it is fragmented as researchers come from different disciplines [7]. Like other Scandinavian countries, Sweden uses the term *samhällskunskap* to refer to social sciences subjects. The complexity of the construction of social sciences education in Sweden and its relationship with citizenship education. The ambiguity arises because on the one hand, social studies is not identified exclusively as citizenship education, but rather is considered a cross-curricular task in Sweden. This means that every subject in school is expected to contribute to the development of democratic citizens. However, on the other hand, the policy explicitly emphasizes handling political, social and economic issues [29], [30]. Sweden is ready to transfer knowledge and values related to liberal democracy and an open economy from one generation to the next. Despite espousing liberal principles, Sweden, along with Norway, Denmark, and Finland, stands out for its universal welfare system a distinctive characteristic recognized internationally as the 'Nordic model'. However, in recent decades, this social democratic welfare state has faced challenges and reforms, with a wave of privatization following.

The structure of the compulsory school curriculum in Sweden consists of three parts for different levels. In grades 1-3, students are first introduced to social sciences as one of the subjects in the 'social sciences' group, along with geography, history, and religious education, for a total of 200 hours of instruction. In years 4-9, these subjects are separated into separate domains with specific teaching hours allocated to each. It is important to note that the 'disciplinary perspective' is reinforced at each stage, and the wording used for grades 7-9 is almost identical to the upper secondary school curriculum. In years 1-6, there was a more general focus on understanding the basic ideas of society, particularly democracy in Sweden [31]. This prafae will further investigate the structure and emphasis of the social studies curriculum in Sweden, highlighting its evolution and implications in primary level education. In summary, we can see the social studies curriculum in Sweden in Table 6, where in the table the position of social studies at each level is explained.

Evolution of core content in social science curricula in Sweden. In years 1-3, the main focus was local phenomena, which evolved into a focus on the public domain in years 4-6. In years 7-9, core content becomes increasingly 'academic' with an emphasis on key concepts in the social sciences domain. This change is also reflected in time allocation, with the four social studies subjects getting significant time in years 1-3, and then becoming more disciplined in years 4-6 and 7-9. It is important to note that the time allocated to grades 4-6 and 7-9 is accompanied by additional time (in brackets above), providing flexibility for teachers to integrate social studies, history, religion, and geography. This prafae will investigate shifts in focus in core content and time allocation in the Swedish social studies curriculum, providing a deeper understanding of the learning approaches used at different school levels [32]. Quoted based on country reports regarding social studies education in Sweden [7], evolution of the social science syllabus structure in Sweden, which started in 2011 and will undergo upcoming reforms in the autumn semester of 2022 (postponed due to COVID-19). In the report, there are three significant changes. First, the most crucial in the context of citizenship education, is strengthening the perspective of community involvement. The 2022 reform can be seen as a return to previous policies, where social studies education played a special role in preparing students for citizenship by focusing on political, economic, and social issues. Second, core content is reduced because teachers have difficulty fitting all the dense core content into the allotted teaching time. Third, there is a shift from ability-based goals to long-term goals formulated as 'knowledge' and 'ability'. This change was the result of a long public debate, in which abilities were seen as 'vague' and too general, so that students may not have acquired sufficient factual knowledge. Based on the description of the social studies curriculum in Sweden, we will try to draw a connection or connection from this social studies curriculum to the attention of the Norwegian government in developing social skills for its students, by

referring to the learning objectives along with the expected competencies and learning methods used by teachers in this country to teach social sciences subjects at grade levels 1-9.

Sweden towards the soft skills aspects of its students, as revealed in the results of the survey ICCS by the international education association (IEA), as seen in Table 7. Sweden particularly stands out in this survey, with children. The 14-year-old Swede demonstrated good knowledge of issues of society, democracy, and citizenship. Sweden's younger generation also displays a solid and positive attitude towards democratic and civic values, with strong support for democratic government. Nonetheless, they follow international trends in becoming less and less involved in formal politics [33].

Table 7. The relationship between social studies curriculum and social skills principles

Level	Learning outcome	Principles of social skills
1-9	The formulated goals and long-term objectives of social studies in compulsory school are the same for all ages;	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
	Strengthening students' democratic citizenship	(1), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
	Developing student familiarity and accumulated experience of democracy and human rights.	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
	Know the values and principles that shape a democratic society as well as democratic processes and procedures.	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)
	An understanding of what it means to be an active and responsible citizen	(1), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)

Source: Curriculum content adapted based on the social studies curriculum in Sweden

3.4. Comparison of social studies curriculum between Denmark, Norway, and Sweden in social skills development

Based on an analytical study of each social studies curriculum in the Scandinavian countries, we can draw a comparison of the three countries in examining the importance of students' social skills through learning social sciences. Where it can be seen from Table 8 that each country meets the seven principal dimensions of social skills, each country seems to have fulfilled each indicator of these skills, whether explicitly reflected in the objectives, methods, social studies materials used or implicitly. Of course, the application and implementation of the social studies curriculum in each country experiences its own ups and downs, but the message that we can get from the description of the social studies curriculum in Scandinavian countries is certainly good practice for us to adopt in increasing the complexity of social studies learning in classrooms. We build. Of course, this still has to be adjusted based on the school climate we live in. We don't necessarily have to adopt the values in this curriculum in our social studies learning, but it can be good practice for developing better social studies learning. Adjusting the curriculum based on culture and school environmental conditions is of course our main concern in developing the curriculum. Reading this article will certainly be an alarm for every practitioner and academic to use as guidance and inspiration in implementing social studies curriculum development wherever we are.

As we see in Table 8, we can see together, in the Scandinavian countries: Denmark, Norway, and Sweden have similar goals in developing students' social skills through an emphasis on democratic citizenship. All countries are committed to developing students who not only understand the concept of democracy but also actively participate in society. All three countries emphasize the teaching of social sciences, including politics, sociology, and economics. This creates a solid foundation for understanding societal structures, political systems, and economics, supporting the development of social skills. Meanwhile, Norway and Sweden show the use of technology in learning as part of their advantages. Both countries have digitalized classrooms, allowing easy access to digital learning resources. As well as Norway and Denmark, although not evenly distributed in every school, show positive practices by involving the community in learning. Community involvement can enrich students' learning experiences and connect learning to the real world.

Denmark stands out for its flexible approach to learning methods. Teachers are given the freedom to choose appropriate theories and approaches, while Norway and Sweden have more structured curricula. In contrast, Norway has a more structured curriculum with a special allocation of teaching hours for social sciences at all levels. This reflects a strong focus on developing social skills from an early age. And Sweden emphasizes a scientific approach to social issues at the high school level. This reflects a focus on developing critical thinking and scientific analysis at a higher level. Although Denmark, Norway, and Sweden have similar goals of improving students' social skills through a social studies curriculum, differences in their approaches, curriculum structures, and teaching practices create their own unique characteristics. Denmark's flexibility, Norway's strong structure, and Sweden's scientific approach mean that each country adapts strategies to suit its educational context and cultural values. The implications that can be concluded based on the overall description above are as follows, which can be seen in Table 9.

Table 8. Social studies curriculum in Scandinavian countries in developing social skills

Country	Principles of social skills	Description
Denmark	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)	<p>This curriculum aims to train students to take an active part in a democratic society. This creates civic awareness and involvement in community decisions</p> <p>Involve students in analysis, presentation, and discussion of social problems. Learning methods such as research projects and debate activities help develop students' analytical and speaking skills.</p> <p>Students who are active in class discussions, can express opinions clearly, and are able to listen to other people's views, demonstrate their ability to interact socially.</p> <p>Small research projects and out-of-class activities, such as visits to organizations or to Parliament, can be indicators of students' ability to work together in groups and collaborate in real-world situations.</p>
Norwegia	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)	<p>Teachers in Norway tend to apply a relaxed and democratic learning approach. This creates more positive interactions between teachers and students, building a more inclusive learning atmosphere.</p> <p>The Norwegian curriculum establishes five basic competencies, including oral skills, writing, reading, numeracy and digital skills. This focus helps students develop social skills comprehensively.</p> <p>Norway has had digitalized classrooms since early 2010, enabling easy access to digital learning resources. The use of this technology helps students connect with the real world and face the demands of the digital age.</p> <p>The Norwegian social studies curriculum stands out in creating a learning environment that supports the development of students' social skills. By integrating a relaxed practice approach, technology, and community engagement, Norway seeks to create students who have not only academic knowledge but also strong social skills to participate in an ever-changing global society. This advantage is in line with the Norwegian government's vision to achieve quality learning and teaching goals by 2025.</p>
Swedia	(1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)	<p>Curriculum goals include strengthening students' democratic citizenship. This reflects a commitment to developing students who have not only theoretical understanding but also active involvement in democratic processes.</p> <p>Long-term goals involve developing students' familiarity with democratic principles and human rights. This shows a commitment to creating a generation that not only knows about democracy but is also actively involved in a democratic society.</p> <p>A teaching style that encourages active participation in elementary school and the 4-9 year level creates a dynamic classroom atmosphere and supports the development of students' social skills.</p> <p>With a scientific approach and emphasis on scientific work, this curriculum forms students who are not only skilled in understanding concepts, but also able to apply their knowledge in real-world contexts.</p>

Table 9. Implications of the social sciences curriculum in Scandinavian Countries

Content	Implications	Description
Democratic citizenship	Encourage a deep understanding of society, politics, economics, and democratic citizenship.	Equips students with a broad understanding of the structure and dynamics of society, providing a foundation for democracy-based global citizenship.
Social and collaboration skills	Integrate group activities, joint projects, and simulations to develop students' social skills.	Build interpersonal, cooperative and effective communication skills to interact well in society.
Openness and diversity	Emphasizes the importance of respecting differences and encouraging an open attitude towards diversity	Respect social, cultural and viewpoint diversity in society.
Critical thinking	Provides space for discussion, debate and in-depth analysis of various perspectives in social studies learning.	Encourage analysis, evaluation and critical thinking skills on social and political issues.
Digital skills and media literacy	Demonstrate the use of technology as an effective learning tool; Integrate media literacy learning and wise use of digital technology in social studies material.	Help students connect to global realities and understand how technology can be used to support learning and participate in a global society; Develop a strong understanding of digital technology and critical skills in consuming and creating media information.
Research and data analysis skills	Encourage small research projects, data analysis, and use of globally accessible information resources.	Develop the ability to compile, carry out and analyze research related to social issues.
Community engagement	Involving the community as part of the learning process.	Develop a sense of social responsibility and involvement in local and global society, helping students understand their role in creating positive change.
Authority and positive teacher-student relationships	Emphasizes the importance of positive relationships between teachers and students, as well as the authority of teachers.	Building a learning environment that supports and motivates students, creating a foundation for student engagement in global education.
Curriculum flexibility and adaptation	Provides flexibility in teaching and curriculum adaptation to local context.	Encourage educational approaches that can be adapted to local and global needs, enabling the integration of local values in a global context.
Education for sustainable development	Including issues of sustainability and environmental preservation in social studies learning to form a generation that cares about the environment.	Encourage understanding of social and environmental responsibility, creating a generation that cares about global issues such as climate change and inequality; Teaches the values of sustainability, social responsibility and environmental impact in decision making.

The innovative and diverse approaches in the Danish, Norwegian, and Swedish social studies curricula have positive implications for global education. They help form students who are not only academically intelligent, but also socially skilled, critical, and ready to contribute to global society. This approach creates a strong foundation for sustainable and relevant learning in a global context. By adopting and developing these values in social studies learning, both in Indonesia and globally, education can play a role in forming a generation that is not only academically intelligent but also has the skills and values needed to contribute positively in an increasingly modern society and world connected.

4. CONCLUSION

Overall, this article summarises key insights from the excellent practices observed in Denmark, Norway, and Sweden, providing concrete recommendations for the improvement of global education. The success of social studies curricula in these Scandinavian countries, which foster students with strong academic and social skills, serves as an inspiring model. The diverse approaches to social skills development revealed in this discussion emphasise the potential for innovative learning methods. It is important to note that this discussion is not only limited to the Nordic context, but also involves comparisons with relevant international research findings and outcomes. These success stories serve as pointers for countries, including Indonesia, seeking to align their education systems with contemporary demands. An integrated approach, flexible selection of theories and incorporation of practical learning methods have proven to be crucial in generating student interest and fostering social skills. Strengthening democratic citizenship, embracing diversity and encouraging community engagement empower students to become agents of positive change in society. In addition, the integration of digital technology and oral exam-based evaluation gives the classroom a modern twist, preparing students for global challenges. Community participation in curriculum development reflects a commitment to creating an education that meets the needs of society and moulds individuals who are ready to make positive contributions at both local and global levels. By adopting these principles, Indonesia can transform social studies education as a whole, preparing students to become future leaders equipped not only with intelligence and insight, but also with the integrity, empathy and social skills needed to navigate the complexities of an ever-changing world. As a result, the social studies curriculum would not just be a series of subjects; rather, it would become the basis of character building, equipping students for a dynamic and optimistic future.

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